

共栖菌群及其产物对“肠-脑轴”中RNA编辑的作用及调控

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演讲者简介

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报告简介

摘要

研究目的：表观遗传是“菌群-肠-脑轴”的重要环节，但RNA编辑在其中的作用尚不明确。本研究拟探究共栖菌群(commensal microbiota, CM)对“肠-脑轴”中RNA编辑的作用及其调控机制。研究方法：比较常规饲养(Conv)和无菌(GF)小鼠的转录组测序数据，对前额叶皮层、海马、杏仁核、脑膜和视网膜等22种细胞、组织和器官的共245个样本进行RNA编辑分析。为进一步验证，对来自粪菌移植(FMT)、单菌定植、脂多糖(LPS)腹腔注射和原代细胞培养模型的498个样本进行常规(bulk)和单细胞转录组测序(scRNA-Seq)分析，加以实验验证。研究结果：(1)与Conv小鼠相比，GF小鼠在多种“肠-脑轴”相关组织和器官中存在显著RNA编辑差异，总体编辑水平下降，且差异编辑基因最主要集中于先天免疫相关功能。大杆菌定植实验，并用细菌产物LPS进行腹腔注射和体外细胞刺激，结合单细胞转录组测序，验证了肠道CM及其产物能显著改变“肠-脑轴”中多种组织的RNA编辑，同样观察到先天免疫相关的功能的富集。(3)最后通过敲低、基因敲除和荧光素酶报告基因等分析

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该系统地阐明了CMI及其产物对“肠-脑轴”中RNA编辑的里安作用并揭示了其调控机制。

Brief introduction

Background: Recent studies have implicated the importance of interplay between microbiota and host epigenetic remodeling in the gut-brain axis. RNA editing is a crucial epigenetic process involved in physiological and pathological conditions, yet its role in the gut-brain axis remains undetermined. Method: RNA editing analysis was conducted using bulk transcriptome sequencing data from conventionally raised (Conv) and germ-free (GF) mice in 236 samples from 28 types of cells, tissues, and organs related to the gut-brain axis, such as the prefrontal cortex, hippocampus, amygdala, meninges, and retina. Our study further confirmed such commensal microbiota-associated RNA editing by using 498 samples from mouse models of fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT), bacterial monocolonization, and lipopolysaccharide (LPS) intraperitoneal injection, and primary cell culture to perform bulk and single-cell transcriptome sequencing (scRNA-Seq) followed by experimental validation. Results: (1) Significant differential RNA editing (DRE) across multiple tissues and organs related to the gut-brain axis was found between GF mice and Conv mice, with an overall decreased average editing level in GF mice. Genes with DRE were mainly involved in innate immunity. (2) Our results of FMT, bacterial monocolonization, intraperitoneal LPS injection, and in vitro LPS stimulation of microglia, followed by scRNA-Seq, confirmed that perturbation and products of gut commensals significantly altered host RNA editing in the gut-brain axis, which was primarily enriched in innate immunity. (3) Finally, the mechanisms of vital regulatory genes and downstream targets of RNA editing were further validated using siRNA knockdown, knockout mice, and luciferase reporter. Our results identified and confirmed that interleukin 12b (IL12b), a hub gene in innate immunity in macrophages, was a key target of microbiota associated RNA editing. Conclusion: Our current study systematically demonstrates the crucial role of commensal microbiota and its products in modulating RNA editing in the gut-

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